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Phenomenological Exploration of Implementation Strategies in Advancing ESD by School Administrators and Educators

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Abstract

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) has become increasingly important as educational institutions worldwide strive to address global sustainability challenges. This study focuses on the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus, exploring how administrators and educators implement ESD and the impact of their strategies on fostering a culture of sustainability. Using in-depth interviews with key figures, including the Dean and Campus Administrator, as well as six professional educators, the study reveals how sustainability concepts are integrated into the curriculum and the practical application of community-based projects. Participants emphasized the value of embedding ESD principles across various subjects rather than treating them as isolated topics, aligning with the views of Sterling (2001) and Tilbury (2011). They also noted the effectiveness of hands-on, community-based learning projects in enhancing students' understanding of sustainability, consistent with Kolb's experiential learning theory. The role of school leaders in setting an example and advocating for sustainable practices emerged as crucial for developing a supportive environment for ESD. Key competencies for principals, such as strategic planning and stakeholder engagement, were identified as essential for effective ESD implementation. However, challenges such as limited resources and resistance to change were noted, highlighting the need for innovative solutions and persistent efforts. This study adds to existing knowledge by providing practical insights into how ESD is operationalized within a specific educational setting and underscores the importance of leadership and comprehensive planning in advancing sustainability goals. These findings offer valuable implications for other institutions seeking to integrate ESD into their educational practices and contribute to the broader discussion on sustainable education.

Keywords: *education for sustainable development, curriculum integration, community-based learning, school leadership, sustainability challenges*

Introduction

Education is constantly evolving, and one of the most important ideas shaping schools today is Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). ESD is an approach that focuses on teaching students how to think critically and act responsibly to build a better and more sustainable future (UNESCO, 2014). It emphasizes the importance of understanding the long-term impact of our actions on the environment and society. At the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus in the Philippines, efforts are being made to apply these global ideas within the specific needs of the local community.

In 2002, the United Nations General Assembly declared the start of the United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development, which took place from 2005 to 2014. The goal of this program, as described by UNESCO (2014), was to help people develop the knowledge and skills needed to understand how their actions affect the world around them and make decisions that support sustainability. Despite some criticism (Jickling & Wals, 2008), this program led to many successful projects that promoted the integration of ESD into schools and other institutions, moving beyond individual efforts to address sustainability at a larger scale (UNESCO, 2014).

One key factor in promoting sustainable development is effective leadership. According to McKeown (2002), leaders must shift away from traditional ways of thinking and adopt more holistic approaches that focus on long-term goals and shared responsibility. This type of leadership encourages collaboration, continuous learning, and ethical decision-making, all of which are crucial for guiding organizations, including schools, toward sustainability (Scott, 2013).

However, even though many international efforts have been made to promote sustainability, there are still challenges when it comes to implementing these ideas in schools. Lozano et al. (2013) point out that while some educational institutions have made progress, many still struggle with how to effectively integrate sustainability into their systems. At the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus, school leaders face unique challenges and opportunities in promoting ESD within their local context. Understanding how these leaders navigate these challenges is essential for improving sustainability efforts in education.

Although research shows that school principals play a crucial role in promoting ESD, there is a lack of studies that provide real-world evidence on how they actually implement sustainability in their schools (Muller, 2020). Most of the existing research is theoretical, focusing on ideas rather than practical examples. Barth and Rieckmann (2016) highlight the need for more studies that explore the actual experiences of school leaders who are responsible for implementing sustainability initiatives. Without this kind of research, it's hard to know how well these ideas work in practice.

This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the real experiences of school administrators at the University of the Visayas Dalaguete

Campus in implementing ESD. Using a phenomenological approach, which focuses on understanding people's lived experiences, this research will look at how these administrators are putting sustainability into practice, the challenges they face, and the strategies they use. By providing this insight, the study hopes to offer a clearer picture of how leadership can support sustainability in education.

Research Questions

In order to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the indispensable role that school administrators play in the progression of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), the purpose of this study is to emphasize a nuanced exploration of the challenges that are encountered and the strategies that are employed in this dynamic process. Specifically, the study aims to address the following inquiries:

1. How do administrators and educators at the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus implement the Education for Sustainable Development?
2. How do administrators actively contribute to cultivating a culture of sustainability within their school?
3. What competencies principals must have to effectively establish ESD initiatives in their schools?

Methodology

Participants

This study focused on key individuals at the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus, specifically the Dean and the Campus Administrator. These participants were selected because of their essential roles in shaping policies, overseeing academic activities, and promoting Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) at the university. Their insights are vital for understanding how ESD is integrated and supported within this academic environment (Creswell, 2014).

In addition to the Dean and Campus Administrator, six professional education educators were also included. Their participation offered a broader perspective on the university's approach to ESD, highlighting the experiences of those directly involved in teaching. This selection aimed to capture diverse viewpoints on how sustainability initiatives are understood and implemented within the institution.

Participants were deliberately chosen based on their roles and contributions to the university's sustainability efforts. The Dean and Campus Administrator were included for their critical influence in policy development and academic oversight. Their views are crucial for grasping the administration's approach to ESD. As noted by Patton (2015), purposeful sampling allows for the selection of individuals who have significant knowledge about the subject being studied.

The six education professionals were chosen to provide insights on the implementation of ESD initiatives from a teaching standpoint. Including both administrative and educational perspectives aimed to create a comprehensive view of the university's sustainability practices.

Instrument

The primary method for data collection in this study was a semi-structured interview guide. This format allowed for in-depth discussions with participants while providing flexibility to explore new topics as they arose. Semi-structured interviews are effective for understanding participants' experiences and perspectives (Creswell, 2014).

The interview guide included open-ended questions that encouraged participants to share their experiences, strategies, and challenges related to Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). This approach led to detailed responses, offering a richer understanding of their involvement in sustainability initiatives (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

To ensure the quality of the interview questions, the guide was validated by two university professors from South Cebu, who provided valuable feedback.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using thematic analysis, a method described by Braun and Clarke (2006). This approach identifies and analyzes patterns or themes within qualitative data, revealing common insights from participants' narratives and providing a deeper understanding of their experiences with ESD.

The analysis process included several systematic steps: familiarizing with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, and defining and naming themes. This process allowed for both deductive and inductive analysis, starting with the research questions while remaining open to new themes that emerged during interviews (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Phenomenology, as outlined by Moustakas (1994), guided this study, enabling an exploration of the essence of participants' lived experiences and their perspectives.

To ensure the credibility and reliability of findings, techniques such as member checking, where participants reviewed the results, and peer debriefing, where colleagues discussed the findings, were used. These methods enhanced the accuracy and trustworthiness of the research outcomes (Creswell, 2014).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings from the in-depth interviews conducted with school administrators and educators at the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus. Through phenomenological analysis, several key themes emerged that address the study's objectives: exploring the implementation of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), understanding the role of administrators in fostering a culture of sustainability, and identifying the necessary competencies for effective ESD initiatives. The findings are discussed in the context of existing literature, providing a comprehensive analysis of how these themes align with or differ from previous studies.

How do administrators and educators at the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus implement Education for Sustainable Development?

Theme 1: Curriculum Integration of Sustainability Concepts

A dominant theme that emerged from the interviews was the integration of sustainability concepts into the existing curriculum. Administrators and educators alike emphasized the importance of embedding ESD principles across various subjects rather than treating them as standalone topics. This approach is consistent with findings from Sterling (2001), who argues that sustainability education should permeate all areas of learning to be truly effective.

Participant A, a principal, noted:

“Gihimo namong priority and pag-integrate sa sustainability sa curriculum, dili separate nga subject pero part sa among existing subjects. Sa aning paagiha, makita sa students giunsa pag apply ang sustainability sa lainlaing aspeto sa ilang mga kinabuhi.”

“We’ve made it a point to integrate sustainability into the curriculum, not as a separate subject but as part of our existing subjects. This way, students can see how sustainability applies to different areas of their lives.”

This aligns with Tilbury (2011), who emphasizes that ESD should be transformative, influencing both the content and process of education. However, this perspective is challenged by a study from Wals and Corcoran (2012), which suggests that without a distinct focus, ESD risks being diluted within the broader curriculum. Despite this concern, the participants in this study largely supported the integrated approach, citing its effectiveness in making sustainability a pervasive and practical aspect of students’ education.

Participant B, an educator, highlighted the relevance of this approach:

“Kasagaran, ang projects og assignments naglibot ra sa mga isyu sa sustainability sa real-world para mas engaging og relevant ang learning process sa mga students.”

“Projects and assignments often revolve around real-world sustainability issues, making the learning process more engaging and relevant for the students.”

This practical application is supported by Mogren, Gericke, and Scherp (2019), who found that students are more likely to engage with sustainability topics when they see direct connections to their own lives and communities. The integration of ESD into the curriculum at the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus reflects a broader trend in education towards making sustainability a core element of learning, although it also raises questions about the balance between integration and focus.

Theme 2: Practical and Community-Based Learning

In addition to curriculum integration, participants highlighted the implementation of practical, community-based learning projects as a key strategy for advancing ESD. This approach aligns with the experiential learning theory proposed by Kolb (1984), which posits that learning is most effective when it involves direct, hands-on experiences.

Participant C shared their experience:

“Among giawhag og giencourage ang mga students to participate o muapil sa mga proyekto sa komunidad about sustainability issues. Kini dili ra makatabang nila sa pagpasabot sa mga concepts but mas maghatag nila og sense of responsibility towards sa ila community.”

“We encourage students to participate in community-based projects that address local sustainability issues. This not only helps them understand the concepts better but also instills a sense of responsibility towards their community.”

This approach is echoed in the work of McKeown and Hopkins (2007), who advocate for community-based learning as a means to connect students with real-world sustainability challenges. The findings of this study support their argument, demonstrating how such projects can enhance students’ understanding of ESD by linking theoretical knowledge with practical application.

However, not all scholars agree on the efficacy of this method. Jickling (2003) cautions that community-based projects, while valuable, can sometimes lack the rigor and depth needed to fully convey complex sustainability concepts. Despite this critique, the participants in this study consistently highlighted the positive impact of these projects on student engagement and learning, suggesting that when properly structured, practical learning experiences are an effective tool for implementing ESD.

How do administrators actively contribute to cultivating a culture of sustainability within their school?

Theme 3: Leadership and Advocacy for a Sustainable School Culture

The role of school administrators in fostering a culture of sustainability emerged as a significant theme, with participants describing how they lead by example and advocate for sustainability initiatives within their schools. This aligns with the leadership theories of Fullan (2001), who argues that effective leaders not only set the vision but also embody the values they wish to instill in their institutions.

Participant D emphasized this point:

“As administrators, we must lead by example. Akong gisiguro nga active nakong iapil ang sustainability initiatives og nag awthag pud ko sa among mga staffs to do the same. Importante kaayo nga ang commitment sa school is sustainability that starts at the top.”

“As administrators, we must lead by example. I make sure to actively participate in sustainability initiatives and encourage my staff to do the same. It’s important that the school’s commitment to sustainability starts at the top.”

This sentiment is supported by the work of Leithwood and Riehl (2003), who found that leadership behavior significantly influences the adoption of new practices, including sustainability initiatives. The participants in this study mirrored these findings, highlighting the critical role that administrators play in setting the tone for ESD within their schools.

Participant E added:

“Naghimo mig policies nga nag promote og sustainable practices across the school, reducing waste to conserving energy. Kani nga policies kay essential para makacreate ta og school-wide culture of sustainability”

“We’ve developed policies that promote sustainable practices across the school, from reducing waste to conserving energy. These policies are essential in creating a school-wide culture of sustainability.”

This approach is consistent with the findings of Hargreaves and Fink (2006), who argue that sustainable leadership involves creating policies and practices that endure beyond the tenure of any individual leader. However, this study also reveals challenges in sustaining these efforts, particularly in the face of resistance from some staff members, which is a concern echoed by Reeves (2009), who discusses the difficulties of implementing lasting change in educational settings.

Overall, the findings suggest that while leadership and advocacy are crucial for cultivating a culture of sustainability, these efforts must be supported by well-crafted policies and a collaborative school environment to achieve long-term success.

What competencies must principals have to effectively establish ESD initiatives in their schools?

Theme 4: Essential Competencies for Effective ESD Implementation

The development of specific competencies among school principals is critical for the successful implementation of ESD initiatives. Participants identified several key competencies, including strategic planning, stakeholder engagement, and environmental literacy, which are necessary for advancing sustainability within their schools.

Participant F highlighted the importance of strategic planning:

“Ang mga principals nagkinahanglan og lig-on nga planning skills para maimplement ang ESD successfully. Naglakip siya og pagset og klaro nga goals, allocating resources wisely jud, og continuous nga pag evaluate sa effectiveness ani nga mga plano.”

“Principals need to have strong strategic planning skills to successfully implement ESD. This involves setting clear goals, allocating resources wisely, and continuously evaluating the effectiveness of our initiatives.”

This finding is consistent with the work of Henderson and Tilbury (2004), who argue that strategic planning is essential for integrating sustainability into educational institutions. The ability to set clear, actionable goals and align resources accordingly is a critical component of effective leadership in ESD.

Participant G discussed the role of stakeholder engagement:

“Ang pag apil sa nagkalain-laing mga stakeholders, lakip niini ang mga magtutudlo, mga estudyante, ginikanan, og of course ang komunidad, kay importante. Ang usa ka principal kinahanglan makahatag og panaghiusa sa mga nagkalainlaing nga grupo aron suportahan ang mga initiatives on ESD.”

“Engaging with various stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and the broader community, is critical. A principal must be able to bring these groups together to support ESD initiatives.”

This perspective aligns with the findings of Burns (2016), who emphasizes the importance of collaboration and communication in successful sustainability initiatives. However, some literature suggests that this competency is often underdeveloped in educational leaders. For instance, Scott and Gough (2003) argue that while principals may recognize the importance of stakeholder engagement,

they often lack the training or experience to do so effectively.

Despite these challenges, the participants in this study demonstrated a strong understanding of the competencies required to lead ESD initiatives, suggesting that with appropriate support and professional development, school leaders can effectively advance sustainability within their institutions.

While the themes discussed thus far provide valuable insights into how ESD is being implemented and the competencies required for effective leadership, the reality of advancing sustainability in educational settings is often fraught with challenges. These challenges, although not the primary focus of this study, emerged as a significant aspect of the participants' experiences, highlighting the complex and multifaceted nature of implementing ESD. Understanding these obstacles is crucial for developing strategies that can overcome them and ensure the successful integration of sustainability into educational practices.

Theme 5: Overcoming Challenges in ESD Implementation

Despite the enthusiasm and commitment expressed by participants, several challenges were identified in the implementation of ESD at the University of the Visayas Dalaguete Campus. These challenges, which include limited resources, resistance to change, and the need for external support, are consistent with findings from other studies on ESD implementation (Tilbury & Wortman, 2004; Cotton, Warren, Maiboroda, & Bailey, 2007).

Participant H discussed the issue of resource limitations:

“Ang among pinakadakong hagit karun mao ang kakulang sa among mga resources. Kung magimplement man gani ta og ESD, nagkinahanglan kini og dako nga budget, which is usahay lisod makuha. Kinahanglan pa mi manaingkamot mayo sa pagpangita og paagi aron makahimo og labaw gamit ang gamay.”

“Our biggest challenge is the lack of resources. Implementing ESD requires funding, which is sometimes difficult to secure. We've had to be very creative in finding ways to do more with less.”

This concern is echoed in the literature, where Tilbury and Wortman (2004) argue that financial constraints are one of the most significant barriers to effective ESD implementation. The need for creative problem-solving and resourcefulness, as described by the participants, aligns with findings from Barth and Rieckmann (2016), who suggest that innovation is often necessary to overcome financial and material limitations in sustainability initiatives.

Participant I pointed out the resistance to change among some staff members:

“Dili tanang maestra o magtutudlo dili ganahan mudawat sa ESD. Naay uban ang pagtan aw nila additional nga trabahuon, so kinihangaln maningkamot mig mayo nga mawala ni sa ilang pagtuo og mapakita usab namo ang importancya sa pagintegrate og sustainability sa ilang pagtudlo.”

“Not all teachers are immediately receptive to ESD. Some view it as an additional burden, so we've had to work hard to change these perceptions and show them the value of integrating sustainability into their teaching.”

This resistance to change is a common challenge in educational reform, as noted by Fullan (2007), who argues that deeply ingrained practices and beliefs can be difficult to shift. However, as the participants in this study indicated, persistent effort and clear communication about the benefits of ESD can help to mitigate this resistance over time.

Finally, the need for external support was highlighted by Participant J:

“Nakita namo ang pakigpartner sa local organizations og mga business kay importante diay kaayo para mabuhat namo ang goals sa ESd. Muprovide sila og financial support og dili ra kana mupaambit sab sila sa ilang nakahimaoan og resources nga dili unta namo ma access.”

“We've found that partnering with local organizations and businesses has been crucial in advancing our ESD goals. They provide not only financial support but also expertise and resources that we wouldn't otherwise have access to.”

This finding supports the argument made by Sterling (2004), who suggests that collaboration with external partners is often necessary for the successful implementation of sustainability initiatives in schools. Such partnerships can provide additional resources, expertise, and legitimacy to ESD efforts, helping to overcome internal limitations and resistance.

Conclusions

Administrators and educators are effectively embedding sustainability into the curriculum by integrating ESD principles across various subjects. This approach ensures that sustainability is not treated as a separate topic but is interwoven into everyday learning. This integration aligns with the views of scholars like Sterling (2001) and Tilbury (2011), who argue that sustainability should be a core part of education to be truly impactful. However, there are differing opinions in the literature, such as Wals and Corcoran (2012), who caution that without a distinct focus, ESD might become diluted. Despite these concerns, the participants in this study find the integrated approach to be beneficial in making sustainability a practical and relevant aspect of students' education.

The study also emphasizes the importance of practical, community-based learning projects in advancing ESD. These projects help students apply theoretical knowledge to real-world issues, fostering a deeper understanding of sustainability. This finding supports the experiential learning theory by Kolb (1984) and is echoed by McKeown and Hopkins (2007), who advocate for hands-on learning as a means to engage students with sustainability challenges. Despite some critiques by Jickling (2003) regarding the depth of community-based projects, the participants in this study found these experiences to be valuable in enhancing student engagement and learning.

The role of administrators in promoting a culture of sustainability is another significant finding. Administrators who lead by example and advocate for sustainability initiatives create a positive environment for ESD. This is consistent with leadership theories by Fullan (2001) and Leithwood and Riehl (2003), which emphasize the influence of leadership behavior on adopting new practices. Participants noted that policies supporting sustainable practices are crucial for creating a school-wide culture of sustainability, although challenges such as resistance from some staff members are acknowledged. This aligns with concerns discussed by Reeves (2009) about implementing lasting change in educational settings.

Finally, the study identifies key competencies that principals need for effective ESD implementation, including strategic planning, stakeholder engagement, and environmental literacy. These competencies are essential for setting goals, involving various groups, and understanding sustainability issues. The findings support the views of Henderson and Tilbury (2004) and Burns (2016), who highlight the importance of these skills. However, challenges in developing these competencies, as noted by Scott and Gough (2003), indicate that additional training and support may be needed for principals to fully realize their role in advancing ESD.

References

- Barth, M., Godemann, J., Rieckmann, M., & Stoltenberg, U. (2007). Developing key competencies for sustainable development in higher education. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 8, 416-430. DOI: 10.1108/14676370710823580
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Bromley, C. (2019). Engaging teachers in sustainability education: Strategies for successful implementation. *Educational Research Review*, 14, 1-9.
- Burns, J. M. (2016). *Transforming leadership: A new pursuit of happiness*. Harvard Business Review Press. https://books.google.com.ph/books/about/Transforming_Leadership.html?id=d5r6dul5Mv0C
- Cotton, D., Warren, M., Maiboroda, O., & Bailey, I. (2007). Sustainable development and higher education: An evidence-based review. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 61(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2273.2007.00320.x>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications. https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_609332/objava_105202/fajlovi/Creswell.pdf
- Davis, J. (2015). Teacher competencies for sustainable development: A framework for ESD in teacher education. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 16(4), 468-485.
- Fullan, M. (2001). *Leading in a culture of change*. Jossey-Bass. <https://www.csus.edu/indiv/j/jelinekd/edte%20227/fullanleadinginacultureofchange.pdf>
- Fullan, M. (2007). *The new meaning of educational change* (4th ed.). Teachers College Press. <https://michaelfullan.ca/books/new-meaning-educational-change/>
- Hargreaves, A., & Fink, D. (2006). *Sustainable leadership*. Jossey-Bass. Retrieved from: <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2005-13851-000>
- Henderson, K. A., & Tilbury, D. (2004). Whole-school approaches to sustainability: A review of the literature. *Australian Journal of Environmental Education*, 20, 47-55. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0814062600001320>
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Prentice Hall. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235701029_Experiential_Learning_Experience_As_The_Source_Of_Learning_And_Development
- Leicht, A., Heiss, J., & Byun, W. J. (2018). *Issues and trends in education for sustainable development*. UNESCO Publishing.
- Leithwood, K., & Riehl, C. (2003). *What we know about successful school leadership*. Laboratory for Student Success. https://olms.ctejhu.org/data/ck/file/What_we_know_about_SchoolLeadership.pdf
- McKeown, R. (2002). *Education for sustainable development toolkit*. UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000152453>
- McKeown, R., & Hopkins, C. (2007). *Education for sustainable development: An introduction*. Routledge. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378088181_educationforsustainabledevelopmentareview

- Meyer, J. W., & Henn, J. (2018). Sustainable development through teacher education: A necessary approach for promoting ESD. *Journal of Education for Sustainable Development*, 12(2), 165-178.
- Mogren, L., Gericke, N., & Scherp, H. (2019). *Sustainability education in schools: An international perspective*. Springer. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/364415468_Implementation_of_Education_for_Sustainable_Development_Through_a_Whole_School_Approach
- Moustakas, C. (1994). *Phenomenological research methods*. Sage Publications. Retrieved from: <https://methods.sagepub.com/book/phenomenological-research-methods>
- Muller, C. (2020). The role of school principals in promoting sustainability: A review of the literature. *Journal of Educational Administration and History*, 52(2), 182-200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220620.2020.1716839>
- Reeves, D. B. (2009). *Leading change in your school: How to conquer myths, build commitment, and get results*. ASCD. Retrieved from: <https://www.amazon.com/Leading-Change-Your-School-Commitment/dp/1416608087>
- Rieckmann, M. (2018). Learning to transform the world: Key competencies in education for sustainable development. In *Handbook of Theory and Practice of Sustainable Development in Higher Education* (pp. 45-60). Springer.
- Scott, W., & Gough, S. (2003). *Learning for sustainable development: An introduction*. Routledge. Retrieved from: <https://researchportal.bath.ac.uk/en/publications/sustainable-development-and-learning-framing-the-issues>
- Sterling, S. (2001). *Sustainable education: Re-visioning learning and change*. Green Books. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289505456_Sustainable_education
- Sterling, S. (2004). *Higher education and sustainability: Challenges, responsibilities, and opportunities*. Higher Education Academy. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227291244_Higher_Education_Sustainability_and_the_Role_of_Systemic_Learning
- Thomas, J. W. (2000). *A review of research on project-based learning*. Autodesk Foundation.
- Tilbury, D. (2011). Education for sustainable development: An overview. In D. Tilbury, J. Stevenson, R. Fien, & A. Schreuder (Eds.), *Education for sustainable development* (pp. 1-15). Routledge. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/255963640_Tilbury_D_2011_'Education_for_Sustainable_Development_An_Expert_Review_of_Processes_and_Learning'_Paris_UNESCO_Available_in_Spanish_French_and_EnglishED-2010WS46
- Tilbury, D., & Wortman, D. (2004). The role of higher education in promoting sustainability: Trends, issues, and strategies. *Australian Journal of Environmental Education*, 20, 47-55. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0814062600001320>
- UNESCO. (2014). *Shaping the future we want: UN decade of education for sustainable development (2005-2014) - Final report*.
- UNESCO. (2017). *Education for Sustainable Development Goals: Learning Objectives*.
- Wals, A. E. J., & Corcoran, P. B. (2012). *Learning for sustainability in times of accelerating change*. Wageningen Academic Publishers. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254833845_Learning_for_sustainability_in_times_of_accelerating_change

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